

CHITOSAN-MODIFIED InGaP/ZnS NANOPARTICLES FOR LIVE CELL IMAGING OF GLIA

M.G. Sandros¹, M. Behrendt², R.A. McKinney³, D. Maysinger³, M. Tabrizian¹

¹Department of Biomedical Engineering, Center for Biorecognition and Biosensors and McGill institute for Advanced Materials, McGill University, 3775 University, Montreal, Qc H3A2B4 (Canada) E-mail: maryam.tabrizian@mcgill.ca. ²Department of Biomedicine, Institute of Anatomy, University of Basel, CH-4056 Basel, Switzerland. ³Department of Pharmacology and Therapeutics, McGill University, 3655 Promenade Sir-William-Osler, Montreal, Quebec, H3G 1Y6, Canada.

ABSTRACT

A wide variety of fluorescent nanoparticles have been recently investigated as bioimaging tools in medicine. This study focuses on new, highly fluorescent chitosan-modified InGaP/ZnS quantum dots (QDs) for examining their intracellular fate in living glial cells. Confocal microscopic studies revealed the distribution of aggregated and non-aggregated chitosan-InGaP/ZnS nanoparticles in live cells together with several cellular organelles. These new polymer modified nanoparticles provide a basis for exploring how surface modifications determine nanoparticle-cell interactions in real-time in neural cells. Additionally, these studies provide a suitable approach to study the intracellular fate of nanomaterials in cells and functional consequences of their co-localization in different cellular compartments.

Glia, Chitosan, InGaP/ZnS, Imaging

INTRODUCTION

The availability of biocompatible, functionalized, stable and highly fluorescent nanoparticles is critical for their use as imaging tools [1]. All current approaches for bioimaging of the nervous system using fixed tissues[2, 3], can result with cell shrinkage and other morphological artifacts. Optical approaches, such as optical molecular imaging (OMI) and gradient index (GRIN) multi-photon microscopy[4, 5] have limited tissue discrimination due to poor resolution. Some bioimaging agents can cause toxicity and fluorescent dyes bleach very quickly[6] and nanobioprobes with dual modalities[7], are currently only beginning to emerge.

Some of the limitations of optical glial/brain imaging with dyes can be overcome by employing luminescent nano-sized particles. However, there is a limited choice of well characterized, highly luminescent quantum dots. A new type of highly luminescent nanoparticles (NPs), indium gallium phosphide (InGaP)/ Zinc Sulfide (ZnS) coated QDs were recently prepared, characterized and functionalized to chitosan [8]. The aim of the work presented here was to investigate Chitosan-InGaP/ZnS NPs co-localization within

different cellular compartments in primary neural cells and to assess the role of chitosan as an organelle-directing agent.

We selected a specific type of chitosan (85:141) with a molecular weight of 141 kDa and a degree of deacetylation of 85 % [8]. This specific type of chitosan polymer is supposed to diminish the assumed QD adverse effects and to enhance the QD cellular uptake. It has been demonstrated in an epithelial cell line Caco-2 cells that chitosans of higher molecular weight and high deacetylation grade support normal cell morphology and maintain physiological intracellular enzyme activity [9, 10]. Previous studies showed that chitosan conjugated or complexed to DNA facilitates DNA entry into nucleus [11]. In contrast, several studies show the use of chitosan as a bioadhesive material which keeps the polymer associated with or in a close proximity of the plasma membrane. The purpose of QD biopolymer surface modification, beside the reduction of cellular toxicity, was to modulate QD-cell interaction. Ligand modified QDs have previously been used to induce receptor mediated endocytosis and to study receptor dynamics in neuron-like cell lines, such as pheochromocytoma PC12 cell lines [12, 13]. Therefore, we assessed the role of chitosan modifications of InGaP/ZnS QDs towards the effect on the subcellular co-localization within primary cortical glia.

RESULTS

Chitosan (Medipol-141 Kda) was covalently bound to InGaP/ZnS in the presence of EDC through the formation of an amide bond [8]. The covalent binding was verified with FT-IR and ¹H-NMR [8]. After encapsulation with chitosan, InGaP/ZnS QDs experienced a red shift in emission from 650 nm to 675 nm due to changes of surface charged states (Figure 1A).

Transmission electron micrograph (TEM) revealed that the average size of bare InGaP/ZnS NPs is between 4 to 5 nm in diameter (Figure 1 B), as for the InGaP/ZnS/Chitosan NPs the average size was around 50 nm containing within up to 16 InGaP/ZnS NPs [8] (Figure 1C). Cell viability with nanoparticle concentration (10 nM) optimized for bio-imaging were analyzed in cortical cultures. Metabolic activity was measured by spectro-fluorometric Alamar blue assay (Figure 1D) in cells incubated with InGaP/ZnS-Chitosan (10 nM, 24 h) in the culture conditioned medium. As shown in Figure 1D, low nanomolar concentrations of nanoparticles did not show significant cell death in the presence of InGaP/ZnS-Chitosan (93.41% ± 13.56) when compared to untreated control (100% ± 1.6).

We used primary cortical glia cells and assessed their extracellular and intracellular state and distribution. An incubation time of 4 hours for NPs for imaging glia was selected, because it was reported that this is sufficiently long time period to allow for nanoparticle internalization and detection in living cells without marked cell loss [14]. A green lysosome-“specific” marker, (LysoTracker green, Molecular Probes) was used in cortical cultures to stain all of the lysosomes (Figure 2). Red nanoparticles formed large aggregates that were hanging at the surface loosely attached to cortical cells labelled by the lysosome marker (Figure 2C, pseudocolored yellow in merged image). There were some red NPs spots not co-localized with lysosomes signifying the participation of other organelles.

Figure 1: (A) Absorbance and fluorescence emission spectra of bare InGaP/ZnS (solid line) and chitosan capped InGaP/ZnS nanoparticles (dashed line, $\lambda_{exc}=520$ nm). Transmission electron micrograph of (B) bare InGaP/ZnS quantum dots and (C) chitosan-InGaP/ZnS nanoparticles at a magnification of 100 K (D) Biocompatibility of InGaP/ZnS-Chitosan NPs in primary cortical cultures. Cell viability in the presence of NPs was assessed by Alamar blue assay. Each bar represents the mean \pm SEM ($n = 3-5$) from at least two independent experiments. Determinations were done after 24 hours of exposure to 10 nM of NPs.

Figure 2: Subcellular localization of InGaP/ZnS-Chitosan NPs with mitochondria in primary cortical cultures after 4h treatment. Live *in vitro* confocal imaging of (A) InGaP/ZnS-Chitosan (10 nM); (B) MitoTracker green FM (1 μ M); (C) overlay A and B.

Another organelle of interest shown previously to be affected by QDs is mitochondria[14]. To study mitochondrial morphology in the presence of NPs, mitochondria were counterstained with a green fluorescent emitting mitochondria-specific dye (MitoTracker, Molecular Probes, Figure 3C). Labelling of cortical glia revealed that none of the chitosan-InGaP/ZnS NPs were associated with mitochondria. There were no drastic changes in the mitochondria structure as observed in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Subcellular localization of InGaP/ZnS-Chitosan NPs with Lysosomes in primary cortical cultures after 4h treatment. Live *in vitro* confocal imaging of (A) InGaP/ZnS-Chitosan (10 nM); (B) LysoTracker green DND 26 (0.5 μM); (C) overlay A and B.

An organelle of great interest with multiple cellular functions is the lipid droplet (LD)[15]. LDs were reported to facilitate interactions between organelles in immune cells by docking and fusing with cell membranes and other organelles such as lysosomes and the endoplasmic reticulum. Ryman-Rasmussen and colleagues suggested that polyethylene glycol coated QDs can be associated with LD in keratinocytes[16]. We therefore counterstained LD with Bodipy 493/503, a green dye, which labels specifically neutral lipids in LD to visualize their co-localization with modified nanoparticles (Molecular Probes, Figure 4). Chitosan-InGaP/ZnS NPs co-localize with LD in glia cells (23%, Figure 4C) suggesting that NPs are inside or on the periphery of LD.

Figure 4: Subcellular localization of InGaP/ZnS-Chitosan NPs in Lipid Droplets in primary cortical cultures after 4h treatment. Live *in vitro* confocal imaging of (A) InGaP/ZnS-Chitosan (10 nM); (B) Bodipy green (0.1mg/ml); (C) overlay A and B.

In addition to the co-localization studies carried out at 4 hours when there was minimal internalization of the chitosan-modified QDs, we investigated whether prolonged incubation time for 8 to 12hours at 37°C would enhance InGaP/ZnS-Chitosan NPs internalization. The cargo of intracellular chitosan modified QDs was clearly evident by

performing triple labeling analysis for QDs (Figure 5A, pseudocolored blue) and was demonstrated to be co-localized more extensively with lysosomes using a red specific-lysosome marker (Figure 5D, pseudocolored pink in merged picture) and with LD (Figure 5D, Bodipy green, pseudocolored yellow in merged picture).

Figure 5: Subcellular localization of InGaP/ZnS±Chitosan with lysosomes and lipid droplets (LD) in primary cortical cultures after 10h of treatment.

DISCUSSION

Chitosan conjugated to InGaP/ZnS QDs formed heterogenous aggregates of different sizes and fluorescence intensities in the proximity of the apical cell membranes (Figures 2-3). After covalently binding chitosan to InGaP/ZnS NPs, the surface charge characteristics of chitosan are altered resulting with a decrease of ionized charged units which are responsible for the effective electrostatic repulsion counteracting hydrophobic aggregation[17]. It is postulated that the presence of salts[17] or any changes in environmental pH[18] can also induce chitosan aggregation. Additionally, the formations of strong inter- and intramolecular hydrogen bonding[19] or dipole-dipole interactions[17] are responsible for chitosan nanoparticle aggregation in vivo and in culture medium at 37 °C after one hour. It is evident that changes in surface charge can provoke several interactions that can be responsible for chitosan modified nanoparticles aggregation. To overcome this aggregation effect, the carrier/cargo (chitosan/NPs) ratio needs to be refined. Previous studies showed that large aggregates of chitosan/DNA complexes prevent penetration of chitosan nanoparticles across epithelial cells within the liver[20].

Overall, the nano-encapsulating materials should be non-cytotoxic, have cell adhesive characteristics and be mechanically stable as well as biocompatible and biodegradable[9]. It is clear from our results that chitosan modification in neural cultures did not induce any toxic effects to primary cells but rather delayed the entry of InGaP/ZnS QDs inside the cell. Prolonged incubation of cells with chitosan-InGaP/ZnS NPs revealed an internalization of NPs with lysosomes and lipid droplets. Results presented here suggest that InGaP/ZnS-

chitosan NPs could be useful in exploring bioadhesive properties of probes in mucous-producing cells such as nasal mucosa or epithelial gut cells[21, 22].

CONCLUSION

In summary, the results obtained from this study present for the first time Chitosan-InGaP/ZnS NPs in live cells in primary cortical cultures. Chitosan-modified InGaP/ZnS NPs formed aggregates and these were found mainly at the cell surface after 4 hours of incubation. In addition, we show that Chitosan-InGaP/ZnS can enter astrocytes and are found in at least two subcellular compartments (lysosomes and lipid droplets) more readily after prolonged incubation (>10 hrs): Chitosan-InGaP/ZnS NPs could be useful as bioadhesive nanoprobe to study their fate after intranasal administration.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

InGaP/ZnS±Chitosan QDs were prepared and characterized as previously described[8]. LysoTracker green DND 26, MitoTracker green, MitoTracker FM and Bodipy was purchased from Invitrogen.

Cell Cultures and Treatments

Cortices of mice (129T2/SV, postnatal day 5) were dissected, removed from meninges, and were pooled from six animals and stored into an ice-cold sterile Ca^{2+} / Mg^{2+} free phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, Gibco). Mechanically, small pieces were separated by gentle trituration using sterile 1 ml pipette tips (PROGENE) and trypsinized with 0.25% Trypsin/EDTA (15050-065, Gibco) at 37°C for 10 min. Separated cells were re-suspended in a solution consisting of DMEM medium (11995-073, Gibco), 10% fetal bovine serum (26140-079, FBS; Gibco) and penicillin/ strepto-mycin/neomycin (PSN) cocktail (15640-055, Gibco). Poly-L-ornithine (P-3655, Sigma) and laminine (L-2020, Sigma) coated 12-mm² glass cover slips (12-545-80, Fisher) were used to seed the cells in suspension and then were incubated in a 95% air/5% CO₂ atmosphere at 37°C. Cells that have attached were then introduced into DMEM medium plus supplements for 24 h in 24-well plates (Corning). The following day, cells were cleaned twice with pre-warmed Neurobasal A media (12349-015, Gibco) and the last step involved a wash step with serum-free Neurobasal A medium containing B27 (17504-044, Gibco), L-glutamine (G-7513, Sigma) and PSN supplements. The cultures were incubated at 37°C in a 95% air/5% CO₂ atmosphere. Following eight days of incubation, cells were introduced to nanoparticles.

Cell Viability Assay

The alamar blue assay procedure was followed in agreement with the spectrofluorimetric method described by[23]. 40 µl of AB reagent/well were added 3 hours before the end of the treatment with NPs in DRG primary cultures yielding a final concentration of 20% (v/v) of the dye in each well in DRGs. After 24 hrs incubation, fluorescence was measured in DRGs. Using a FLUOstar OPTIMA spectrofluorometer, the plates were excited with a 535

nm wavelength and emission was collected at 580 nm. The percent viability was tabulated by comparing the fluorescence intensity of the treated cells compared to untreated control in RPMI 1640 medium. After collecting data from 2 independent experiments, the values were corrected from background fluorescence and were compiled and characterized by ANOVA.

Confocal Microscopy

Confocal images were taken with a Zeiss LSM 510 NLO inverted microscope. A 695/40 nm bandpass filter was used along with a violet laser for excitation to enhance the detection conditions for InGaP QDs. Cells were harvested on 12-mm² glass cover slips in 24-well chambers (1.83.1836; Sarstedt). NPs were added to designated wells and the cells were incubated for different time periods.

Statistical Analysis

SYSTAT 10 (SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA) was used to analyze all compiled results. Statistical significance was resolved by Student's t-test, 1-way ANOVA followed by multiparametric Dunett's post-hoc test, or 2-way ANOVA. Differences were considered significant where $p < 0.05$.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank Canadian Institutes of Health Research, Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada and National Science Research Council and American Alzheimer's Association for partial financial support.

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